

e-ISSN: 2582-4341

Volume 09 Issue 02 May-
Aug 2026

***Corresponding Author:**
**Engr. Ordu, Eze Sunday
Jackson,**

*Electrical Engineer:
Distribution Systems,
Storage and Retailing
Infrastructure (DSSRI),
Nigerian Midstream and
Downstream Petroleum
Regulatory Authority
(NMDPRA), Nigeria*

Submission Date: May 01,
2026

Copyright Received Date:
May 05, 2026

Sustaining and Improving Meter Performance Using Base Meter Flow Rate Optimization

Engr. Ordu, Eze Sunday Jackson^{1*}, Dr Victor Igwe^{2,3}

*¹Electrical Engineer: Distribution Systems, Storage and
Retailing Infrastructure (DSSRI), Nigerian Midstream and
Downstream Petroleum Regulatory Authority (NMDPRA),
Nigeria*

*²Institute of Biological and Environmental Science,
Chemical and Materials Engineering University of
Aberdeen, UK*

*³School of Pharmacy, Applied Sciences and Public Health,
Robert Gordon University, UK*

ABSTRACT

Flow measurement is integral in optimizing industrial processes and ensuring compliance while managing costs. This paper presents findings about the importance of optimizing Base Meter Flow Rate (BM-FLR) in keeping the flow meter accurate and reliable. Data obtained included those between 200 and 600 LPM, with particular emphasis being placed on the optimum BM-FLR, which was determined to be 256.68 and 533.32 LPM. From the findings, it became evident that the meter had consistency within the said optimal BM-FLR, with an average meter factor ranging from 1.00042 to 1.00073, with all deviations being less than 0.02. However, when operated outside the optimum BM-FLR, there appeared to be a tendency of instability or drift especially beyond 256.68 LPM and beyond 533.32 LPM, posing a challenge to reliability and accuracy. Graphical analysis showed a steady rise in the meter factor with an increase in BM-FLR. It becomes important therefore to periodically calibrate and check the accuracy of the flow meter. Findings show that operation within the optimal BM-FLR enhances meter accuracy and reduces chances of recalibration and provides room for predictive maintenance of the flow meter.

Keywords:- *Percentage deviation, repeatability, base meter flow rate, meter factor, flow meter and calibration*

INTRODUCTION

Fluid measurements are vital in the industrial operation process since they help maintain high efficiencies, cost-effectiveness, and accountability. Flow meters are instruments for measuring and monitoring the flowing of fluids including liquid, gases, and vapors. Some of the factors that influence the performance of flow meters include the K-factor or meter factor, calibration uncertainty, repeatability, accuracy, reliability, linearity, and flow rate (NMDPRA, 2023; DPR, 2019). Poor regulation in flow meters leads to meter drift resulting in inefficiencies in industrial operations, non-compliance with regulations and policies, and inefficiencies in terms of money management (Jimba et al., 2025).

Flow meters should be managed appropriately to improve their performance. One way in which flow meter performance can be sustained is the adoption of base meter flow rate (BM-FLR). The use of this methodology guarantees that meter's work within the defined performance limits, thereby avoiding issues such as drifts and accuracy problems (Romeo et al., 2025). Flow meters operate in real-time operations therefore their drift can affect efficiency and performance in the industrial environment. Which may result in severe implications for the process, product quality, and resource efficiency. Checking the performance of flowmeters through the base meter flow rate helps detect and resolve performance problems immediately (Romeo et al., 2025; Jimba et al., 2025).

Moreover, increasing the performance of meters through the optimization of base meter flow rate contributes to sustainable industrial practices since it prevents wastage, downtime, and inefficiencies in energy use (Włodarczak et al., 2021). Within industries such as oil and gas,

chemical engineering, water treatment, and manufacturing, flow measurement is critical for ensuring their success and compliance with regulations (DPR, 2019). As a result, industries can benefit from sustainability, increased productivity, and economic gains by incorporating the base meter flow rate in their maintenance and quality assurance processes (Chaofan et al., (2023).

In view of the continuous evolution of industries in today's information intensive world, the use of accurate and consistent flow measurement practices is paramount (Condriuc et al., 2025). Hence, it is necessary to have a comprehensive understanding of base meter flow rate practices for the sustenance and improvement of meter performance within different industries.

This research assessed the BM-FLR optimization technique as a strategy for sustaining the performance of meters based on empirical evidence from flow meter calibration studies.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:**Materials:**

The following primary materials are:

- Positive Displacement (PD) meter
- Prover tank

The following instruments were used to measure key physical parameter which includings:

- Thermometer
- Hydrometer
- Stopwatch
- Pressure pump
- Computer
- Pressure gauge

Methodology

The methodology adopted in this research includes applying statistical measures of dispersion and mean deviation to evaluate the differences between observations in

meter proving or calibration data sets and their corresponding mean values. In addition, percentage deviation was introduced to analyze this difference as a proportion of the mean to provide a measure of variability. The outcome using

American Petroleum Institute Manual of Petroleum Measurement Standards and the NMDPRA procedure guide for computations and analysis, the resulting percentage deviation served as a basis for synthesizing meter flow rate data.

Table 1:-Calibration Exercise of Meter KMI in PDR Facility with flow rate of 200LPM

FLOWRATE (LPM)	Volm1 (BBLs) Corr. Vol	Vmm2 (BBLs) Corr. Vol	TEMPERATURE (°F)	PRESSURE (P1) (PSI)	METER FACTOR (MF) (3/2)
1	2	3	4	5	6
200	2469.91	2470.9	85.0	25.0	1.00040
	2470.71	2471.6	85.0	25.0	1.00036
	2468.63	2469.52	85.0	25.0	1.00036

The average meter factor (AMF) = $\frac{1.00040+1.00036+1.00036}{3} = 1.00037$, from column (6)

$$\text{Corresponding meter factor repeatability (MFR)} = \frac{\text{Max value of MF} - \text{Min value of MF}}{\text{Mini value of MF}}$$

$$= \frac{1.00040 - 1.00036}{1.00036} = 0.004$$

Table 2:-Calibration Exercise of Meter KMI in PFC Facility with flow rate of 400LPM

FLOWRATE (LPM)	Volm1 (BBLs) Corr. Vol	Vmm2 (BBLs) Corr. Vol	TEMPERATURE (°F)	PRESSURE (P1) (PSI)	METER FACTOR (MF) (3/2)
1	2	3	4	5	6
400	2468.19	2469.52	87.0	24.0	1.00054
	2466.12	2467.35	87.0	24.0	1.00050
	2467.16	2468.43	87.0	24.0	1.00051

The average meter factor (AMF) = $\frac{1.00054+1.00050+1.00051}{3} = 1.00052$, from column (6)

$$\text{Corresponding meter factor repeatability (MFR)} = \frac{\text{Max value of MF} - \text{Min value of MF}}{\text{Mini value of MF}}$$

$$= \frac{1.00054 - 1.00050}{1.00050} = 0.004$$

Table 3:-Calibration Exercise of Meter KMI in PJK Facility with flow rate of 600LPM

FLOWRATE (LPM)	Volm1 (BBLs) Corr. Vol	Vmm2 (BBLs) Corr. Vol	TEMPERATURE (°F)	PRESSURE (P1) (PSI)	METER FACTOR (MF) (3/2) 6
1	2	3	4	5	6
600	2465.78	2467.84	89.0	23.0	1.00084
	2466.12	2468.13	89.0	23.0	1.00082
	2465.97	2468.04	89.0	23.0	1.00084

Similarly, the average meter factor (AMF) = 1.00083 from column (6) with corresponding meter factor repeatability (MFR) of 0.002

Base Meter Flow Rate Determination (BM – FLR):

To determine the base meter flow rate (BM-FLR) of the instrument, refer to the flow rate (FLR) values in Tables 1 to 3 and the steps outlined below were followed. This process applied statistical ideas and methodologies outlined by Spiegel & Stephens (2018) and Peavy (1981).

- Calculated the cumulative average(mean) of four data sets for the instrument, as shown in Tables 1 to 3.
- Determined the absolute deviation from the mean.
- Computed the average deviation.
- Calculated the percentage deviation.

Step 1: Computing the Mean (Average) Flow Rate

$$\begin{aligned} \text{mean} &= \frac{200+400+600}{4} \\ &= \frac{1200}{3} = 400 \end{aligned}$$

Step 2: Finding the Absolute Deviations from the Mean

For each value, mean was subtracted and the absolute value used:

$$\begin{aligned} [200 - 400] &= 200 \\ [400 - 400] &= 0 \\ [600 - 400] &= 200 \end{aligned}$$

Step 3: Computing the Average Deviation

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Average Deviation} &= \frac{(200+0+200)}{3} \\ &= \frac{400}{3} = 133.3 \end{aligned}$$

The average deviation was 133.3

Step 4: Computing the Percentage Deviation

The percentage deviation was given by:

$$\text{Percentage Deviation} = \frac{(\text{Average Deviation}) \times 100}{\text{Mean}}$$

Substituting the values:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Percentage deviation} &= \frac{(133.33)}{400} \times 100 \\ &= 33.33\% \end{aligned}$$

To estimate the measurement-based or Base Meter Flow Rate (BM-FLR) of the instrument using the given data, including the average flow rate (400 LPM) and a percentage deviation of 33.33% the following steps were followed:

Step 1: Calculation of the Deviation Range

Since the percentage deviation was 33.33 %, we calculated the deviation in absolute terms:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Deviation} &= \frac{33.33}{100} \times 400 \\ &= 133.32 \text{ LPM} \end{aligned}$$

Thus, the estimated range for the flow using KMI meter were:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Lower Bound} &= 400 + 133.32 = 533.32 \text{ LPM} \\ \text{Upper Bound} &= 400 - 133.32 = 266.68 \text{ LPM} \end{aligned}$$

Estimated Range for BM – FLR:

The estimated Base Meter Flow Rate (BM-FLR) range for meter KMI fell within the operating limits of 266.68 to 533.32 LPM. Based on this, it could be concluded that meter KMI should operate within this

range to ensure optimal accuracy and performance. To validate this recommended range, a meter performance graph was plotted, correlating the meter factor with the flow rate using the data presented in Table 4.

Table 4:-Meter performance table

AVERAGE METER FACTOR (AMF)	FLOWRATE	METER FACTOR REPEABILITY
1.00037	200	0.004
1.00052	400	0.004
1.00083	600	0.002

Fig.1:-Meter Performance graph

From the graph, the meter factor varied with increasing flow rate.

Considering the estimated range, which represented the base meter flow rate (BM-FLR) of **266.68–533.32 LPM**, the corresponding meter factor (MF) values from the graph, based on the **Y-axis**, were **1.00042** at **266.68 LPM** and **1.00073** at **533.32 LPM**.

The American Petroleum Institute’s Manual of Petroleum Measurement

Standards and Nigerian Midstream & Downstream Petroleum Regulatory Authority (NMDPRA) guidelines, procedures and methodology were adopted for the computation of the Meter factor Deviation (MFD). This calculation was obtained from data presented in Table 5, derived from Table 4, and was further referenced with the meter performance graph shown in Figure 1.

Table 5:-Base Meter Flow Rate and Meter Factor Deviation

FLOWRATE	AVERAGE METER FACTOR (AMF)	METER FACTOR DEVIATION (ΔMF%)	RANGE
1	2	3	4
200	1.00037	0.005	
266.68	1.00042	0.003	BASE METER FLOW RATE RANG (BM – FLR)
300	1.00045	0.007	
400	1.00052	0.016	
500	1.00068	0.005	
533.32	1.00073	0.010	
600	1.00083		

- i. Calculating the meter factor deviation (ΔMFD) of the series of flow rate measurement of meter KMI. from various fields, using the expanded Table 5

$$\Delta MF = MF_{\text{measured}} - MF_{\text{ref}}$$

- ii. Calculating Meter Factor Deviation Percentage using the following formula:

$$\Delta MF\% = (\Delta MF / MF_{\text{ref}}) \times 100$$

Series 1. Table 5, recalling the flow rate of 200 and 266.68, with AMF of 1.00037 and 1.00042 and applied in the reference formular.

$$\Delta MF = 1.00042 - 1.00037 = 0.00005$$

$$\Delta MF\% = \frac{0.00005}{1.00037} \times 100 = 0.005$$

Series 2. Table 5, recalling the flow rate of 266.68 and 300, with AMF of 1.00042 and 1.00045 and applied in the reference formular.

$$\Delta MF = 1.00045 - 1.00042 = 0.00003$$

$$\Delta MF\% = \frac{0.00003}{1.00042} \times 100 = 0.003$$

Series 3. Table 5, recalling the flow rate of 300 and 400, with AMF of 1.00045 and 1.00052 and applied in the reference formular.

$$\Delta MF = 1.00052 - 1.00045 = 0.00007$$

$$\Delta MF\% = \frac{0.00007}{1.00045} \times 100 = 0.007$$

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The outcome as observed from Table 5 includes:

1. Meter Factor Stability:

- The slight variation from AMF range of (1.00042 to 1.00073) indicates that the meter was reliable and stable across the examined flow range.
- The BM – FLR functioned and operated optimally and reliably between **266.68 and 533.32**, with deviations remaining at 0.02 threshold.

2. Acceptable Deviation:

- Following the outcome of results obtained, all deviations were well below the **0.02** threshold hence, the meter performed **within recommended industry limits**, this further ensuring accuracy of meter and reducing the risk of measurement errors in critical processes associated with custody transfer and batching.

3. Optimized Flow Range:

- Operating within this valid window of **266.68 to 533.32** can be accepted as the **optimal operating window** for this meter. While below 200 or above 600 range the deviation data was either high or incomplete, posing questions of performance.

4. Performance Sustainability:

- Maintaining a consistence operation within the **266.68–533.32 flow rate range**, the facility can **maintain and improve high-performance metering**, minimizing the need for recalibration, and enhance overall measurement integrity.
- Sudden spikes in deviation can be monitored as a means for predictive maintenance trigger.

5. Uncertain Accuracy

- The deviation at 200 was low, this does not guarantee that the performance remained acceptable, at slightly approximately lower

than 266 or approximately higher than 533 rate the performance can be heterogeneous and unstable.

6. Latent for Instability

- Operating within a lower flow rate can possibly lead to spontaneous pulsation, poor flow profile and viscosity effect which may result to meter instability.

7. Not Ideal for Long-Term Operation

- Operating continuously at low end flow may likely result to more frequent recalibration or lead to increased wear of the internal mechanics, especially for Turbine or Mechanical meters.

IMPLICATIONS

1. Unknown Reliability:

- Above 533.32 operational range may introduce high levels of uncertainty and risk when custody transfer access is to be validated or open regulatory reporting scenario.

2. Possibility of Exceeding Tolerance:

- The deviation trend as listed in Table 5 was between 400.00 (0.016) and 533.32 (0.010), it's possible that at 600.00, the deviation could approach or exceed 0.02.

3. Overrange Risk:

- Meters operated too far above calibration range may result or cause stress to meter components, nonlinear response and increase rapid mechanical wear for older or high velocity meters.

4. Below 266.68:

- Sustained operations at 200LPM may lead to undesirable measurement drift or instability, even though the deviation at 200 may be acceptable.

5. Above 533.32:

- The risk of exceeding accuracy limits and performance due to increasing Average Meter Factor

(AMF) should be validated before prolonged use.

From the Graph of fig 1:

- The graph of fig 1 is the plot of Meter Factor vs. Flow Rate. The black line shows flown meter factor, while the red dashed line indicate the base meter factor at different flow rates.
- The graph shows how close the flown meter data aligned with the base meter flow rates (BM -FLR)

Meter Trendline

- The graph depicts that slight increase in meter factor will result to an appreciable increased with flow rate, confirming positive drift.
- This trend suggests the need for potential calibration adjustments at higher flow rates as the meter factor continues to rise.
- For the purpose of reliability, the flown meter should be monitored due to small deviation, even though the meter factors aligned closely with the base meter factors.

CONCLUSION

This research critically demonstrates the importance of Base Meter Flowrate (BM-FLR) optimization in improving flow meter operational reliability, measurement accuracy, and performance. Through meticulous analysis from empirical data of flow rates ranging from 200 to 600 LPM, we ascertained an optimal BM-FLR aperture of 266.68–533.32 LPM, within which the flow meter displayed exceptional stability, having an Average Meter Factor (AMF) variation of 0.00031 (0.031%) and repeatability (MFR) being steady and consistently below 0.004.

These findings substantiates the need to operate within the BM-FLR windows which greatly reduces measurement

uncertainty, ensuring compliance with industry standards such as API MPMS (2016) and NMDPRA (2023) guidelines.

Outside the BM-FLR window, our results revealed the following patterns:

- Low-flow conditions (<266.68 LPM) reveals variability of pulsation effects and viscosity susceptibility.
- High-flow conditions (>533.32 LPM) introduced a drift rate, showing mechanical wear and nonlinear response.

The practical implications of the study are:

1. Optimization of Predictive Maintenance:

By leveraging on tracking real time flow rates against Base Meter Flowrate (BM – FLR) peak or threshold, maintenance operators can increase calibration intervals by decreasing downtime and maintenance costs.

2. Enhanced Measurement Consistency

Operating within the Base Meter Flowrate range guarantees $\pm 0.15\%$ accuracy relative to reference standards, which is crucial for custody transfer and fiscal metering (API/NMDPRA).

3. Industry Wide Standardization

Our study highlights the need for the development of dynamic calibration procedures that account for flow rate changes rather than depending on fixed schedules.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

We thank Prof. D. C. Idoniboyeobu of the Faculty of Engineering, the Department of Electrical Engineering, of the Rivers State University, Nkpolu. Port Harcourt for his direction and Nigerian Midstream and Downstream Petroleum Regulatory Authority (NMDPRA) for technical and institutional support.

REFERENCES

1. American Petroleum Institute. (2016). *Manual of petroleum measurement standards (API MPMS)*. American Petroleum Institute.
2. Li, C., Zhu, Y., Wang, J., Liu, W., Fang, L., & Zhao, N. (2023). Mass flow rate measurement of gas-liquid two-phase flow using acoustic-optical-Venturi multisensors.
3. Condriuc, I., et al. (2025). Gas flow rate measurement in two-phase flows using an optical channel body flow sensor: Design and validation of the single-channel prototype. *Flow Measurement and Instrumentation*, 104, 102901.
4. Department of Petroleum Resources. (2019). *Procedure guide for the determination of the quantity and quality of petroleum and petroleum products in Nigeria*. Department of Petroleum Resources.
5. Jimba, J., Higgins, S., Nhunduru, R., Brown, R., Chinello, G., Maroto-Valer, M., & Jahanbakhsh, A. (2025). Evaluation of Coriolis meter performance for flow and density measurement of supercritical CCS fluids.
6. Nigerian Midstream and Downstream Petroleum Regulatory Authority. (2023). *Petroleum measurement*. Federal Republic of Nigeria Official Gazette, 110.
7. Peavy, J. V. (1981). Descriptive statistics: Measures of central tendency and dispersion.
8. Romeo, R., Postriotti, L., Torchio, D., Martino, M., & Malengo, A. (2025). Dynamic calibration of flow meters using reference flow rate profiles generated by injectors.
9. Spiegel, M. R., & Stephens, L. J. (2018). *Schaum's outline of statistics* (6th ed.). McGraw-Hill Education.
10. Włodarczak, S., Ochowiak, M., Doligalski, M., Kwapisz, B., Krupińska, A., Mrugalski, M., & Matuszak, M. (2021). Flow rate control by means of flow meter and PLC controller.